

**TEACHING INTERPRETATION OF PRECEDENT PHENOMENA IN
THE COURSE OF READING ENGLISH LITERARY TEXTS****Erkinova Sokhiba Ravshanovna**

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

esohiba85@gmail.com

Abstract: This article is devoted to study the role and place of precedent phenomena in order to develop and improve the foreign language socio-cultural competence of students, their use as an effective means of expanding the subject-thematic base for mastering different types of speech activity and obtaining objective socio-cultural information about the daily life of representatives of large and small social groups of the country of the studied language. Also, to reveal the linguistic and methodological characteristics of precedent phenomena in English language as objects of assimilation in practical classes on the practice of oral speech of the target language. Moreover, to design a system of exercises for the assimilation of precedent phenomena in order to improve the structural components of foreign-language socio-cultural competence.

Key words: precedent phenomena, precedent text, socio-cultural competence, pedagogical interaction, stereotypes, culture, religion.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola talabalarning chet tilidagi ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentsiyasini rivojlantirish va takomillashtirish maqsadida pretsedent hodisalarning roli va o'rnini o'rganishga, ulardan nutq faoliyatining har xil turlarini o'zlashtirish va kundalik hayot to'g'risida ob'ektiv ijtimoiy-madaniy ma'lumotlarni olish uchun mavzu-tematik bazani kengaytirishning samarali vositasi sifatida foydalanishga bag'ishlangan. Shuningdek, maqsadli tilning og'zaki nutqi amaliyoti bo'yicha amaliy mashg'ulotlarda assimilyatsiya ob'ekti sifatida ingliz tilidagi pretsedent hodisalarning lingvistik va uslubiy xususiyatlarini ochib berish vazifasini ham bajaradi. Bundan tashqari, chet tilidagi ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentsiyaning tarkibiy

qismlarini takomillashtirish maqsadida pretsedent hodisalarni o'zlashtirish uchun mashqlar tizimini taklif qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: pretsedent hodisalar, pretsedent matn, ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentsiya, pedagogik o'zaro ta'sir, stereotiplar, madaniyat, din.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена изучению роли и места прецедентных феноменов с целью развития и совершенствования иноязычной социокультурной компетенции студентов, их использованию как эффективного средства расширения предметно-тематической базы для овладения различными видами речевой деятельности и получения объективной социокультурной информации о повседневной жизни представителей больших и малых социальных групп страны изучаемого языка. Также выявить лингвистические и методологические характеристики прецедентных явлений в английском языке как объектов усвоения на практических занятиях по практике устной речи изучаемого языка. Кроме того, разработать систему упражнений для усвоения прецедентных явлений с целью совершенствования структурных компонентов иноязычной социокультурной компетенции.

Ключевые слова: прецедентные феномены, прецедентный текст, социокультурная компетентность, педагогическое взаимодействие, стереотипы, культура, религия.

INTRODUCTION

The sociocultural approach describes the process of intercultural interaction, showing not only the concepts of a common or national culture, but also the social sphere, as well as the stereotypes of everyday life. Communication in the studied language is provided not only by the possession of language and speech competence, but also socio-cultural. The skills and abilities of adequate communication at the cultural level formed at the university in the future will become the foundation for self-realization in the professional sphere, thus, the possession of socio-cultural competence is an integral component of the professionalism of a foreign language teacher.

Socio-cultural competence has its own component composition. Mastery of individual components of socio-cultural competence allows students to communicate without failures with representatives of various linguistic communities of the country of the studied language and overcome constantly emerging cultural barriers. The content of the components of socio-cultural competence shows that precedent phenomena are an integral component in the development of this type of competence. Precedent phenomena permeate and fill almost all components of socio-cultural competence. In addition, they are the content base of many speech actions of representatives of large and small social groups of the country of the language being studied. The meaning of native speakers' statements is almost always expressed implicitly. It can often be incomprehensible to representatives of another linguistic and cultural community, for example, Uzbek. Students as future language teachers should be able to adequately perceive statements with such phenomena. The student must learn how to convey the meaning and interpret the meaning of perceived phenomena, correctly use them in speech communication with different groups of people who operate with such phenomena in their speech.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to overcome socio-cultural difficulties, therefore, it is necessary to know deeply not only the specifics of the country of the language being studied, which is contained in background knowledge, in knowledge of the realities of the country, but also the features of the speech repertoire of small groups, knowledge of precedent phenomena that members of such social groups and collectives often use in their speech communication and behavior.

Hence, the role and importance of socio-cultural competence in the educational process of a foreign language in a pedagogical university increases. This type of competence, along with other types of competencies, is implemented in the oral and written speech of future teachers. There are increased requirements for the level of possession of socio-cultural competence. Serious requirements are placed on the development and improvement of skills and abilities for the conscious use in speech of

all components of the structure of socio-cultural competence. Knowledge of speech and behavioral stereotypes from the daily life of representatives of large and small social groups of the country of the language being studied (schoolchildren, students, workers, representatives of the academic environment, representatives of culture, religion, business and political circles) not only expand the socio-cultural horizons of students, but also significantly enrich their linguistic and speech experience in the use of language and speech which function in life, in everyday activities, in speech communication of representatives of various groups – native speakers of the studied language.

The main thing of improving the socio-cultural competence of future foreign language teachers is, first of all, working with authentic texts. The texts contain relevant socio-cultural information, linguistic and sociolinguistic vocabulary, sociocultural stereotypes of non-verbal behavior. They represent the English-speaking world from different societies, native speakers.

In authentic English-language texts, country-specific marked language units' function. There are also culturally marked precedent phenomena in them. The phenomena give a vivid linguistic characteristic to representatives of small and large social groups speaking the language being studied. For educational purposes, it is important to correctly select authentic texts with such phenomena. Examples of precedent texts can be literary works ("Alice in Wonderland"), jokes, lyrics, advertising, names of paintings ("Mona Lisa"), idioms ("Rome was not built in a day").

Precedent phenomena are sociocultural signs reflecting facts, events, situations known to representatives of a certain linguistic and cultural community, which have a super personal character, are renewed in the discourse of a particular personality and have value significance. Precedent phenomena have the following linguistic and methodological characteristics: 1) factual; 2) referential; 3) axiological labeling; 4) repeatability; 5) clichéd; 6) reference; 7) chaotic way of existence; 8) chronotropic labeling.

The mastery of precedent phenomena plays a key role in the development of socio-cultural competence of students of pedagogical directions. The constant recurrence of precedent phenomena in the speech of native speakers is important. Such a property of phenomena is reflected in the speech of students as future language teachers. Knowledge of precedent phenomena and the ability to operate with them indicates the information awareness of the teacher, his socio-cultural competence, that is, the ability to behave in accordance with the social conventions of this speech community. A student, a future English teacher, must show his ability to recognize and imitate the language and behavioral patterns of speakers of another language culture. Mastering the precedent phenomena is a definite incentive for students to learn the culture and language of small groups and communities as native speakers.

The implementation of the educational process within the framework of the socio-cultural approach contributes to the establishment of intersubjective and interdisciplinary connections in teaching a foreign language as a means of real intercultural communication with its native speakers, as a reliable pedagogical and methodological tool for the future pedagogical activity of a teacher at school and a teacher at a university.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis show that principles, content of teaching, methods, methods, techniques and forms of work in language classes determine the success of pedagogical interaction between the teacher and students. All pedagogical interaction of the teacher and students is built within the framework of the study on the basis of special methodological principles. Here are the principles of improving socio-cultural competence in classes on the practice of oral and written speech in English:

- 1) the principle of solving communicative tasks on the basis of socio-cultural information contained in precedent phenomena;
- 2) the principle of socio-cultural visibility of the presentation of precedent phenomena;
- 3) the principle of unity of speech situations and the socio-cultural background used;
- 4) the principle of authenticity of precedent phenomena;

- 5) the principle of interaction of foreign language and native culture of students;
- 6) the principle of dominance of problematic tasks of a socio-cultural nature;
- 7) the principle of taking into account the specifics of the social culture of small groups and its linguistic equipment with precedent phenomena.

Within the framework of experimental training, training technologies have been selected and adapted for the purposes of the research, which are described in the dissertation research. They are aimed at improving socio-cultural competence: 1) the technology of problem-based learning; 2) the technology of discussing a socio-cultural event; 3) the portfolio of linguistic and socio-cultural material; 4) the technology of the festival of cultures of small groups; 5) the technology of critical thinking.

In the process of research in this direction, several exercises were developed on the topic that we are considering. Here are examples of some exercises:

- Read the precedent quotation and write an essay using cultural marked words correctly and paying attention to the linguistic peculiarities of social groups.
- Read the socio-cultural situation and make up a dialogue with your partner using socio-cultural aspects accepted in English culture in your speech.
- Watch a video about socio-cultural peculiarities of a foreign country, act out the situations you have watched using precedent phenomena.
- Take part in a role-play on the topic, use precedent phenomena in your speech.

To be more clear teachers can conduct next activities as role-play games. The game assumed the inclusion in its content and in the linguistic equipment of all the language and speech material passed. Before conducting the games students are offered to watch a video about culture of one of English speaking countries and text top read. After that, students perform a series of exercises on the text: 1. Underline precedent phenomena and explain their meaning. 2. Make up your own sentences with precedent phenomena. 3. Define the style of the text. 4. Work in pairs and discuss with your partner life hacks that you use during lockdown. 5. Take part in a Role play.

CONCLUSION

The process of intensification of language teaching due to precedent phenomena in the improvement of socio-cultural competence can be considered as research prospects; further study of this construct in relation to other areas of training of students of specialized universities; adaptation of the developed teaching methodology to precedent phenomena for the development of socio-cultural competence of students of non-core universities; creation of a distance course on the proposed methodology for improving socio-cultural competence. A system of exercises for the assimilation of precedent phenomena in order to improve the structural components of foreign-language socio-cultural competence gives positive results.

Materials that have been investigated in this article can be beneficial in cross-cultural analysis of precedent phenomena functioning in English literary texts that enlarge world picture of the native speakers and contribute to development of contrastive linguistics. Also, designed materials can be used in the lecture courses of Lexicology, Cultural Linguistics (linguoculturology), Intercultural communication and in the practice of teaching English as specialty. Besides, the results of investigation can be also used while research activity and course books designing.

REFERENCES

1. Zolotarev M. Precedent Phenomena: The role of Cultural Reference in Dostoevsky's novel *Demons*// thesis. 2013. 2-80.
2. Гудков Д. Б. Прецедентная ситуация и способы ее актуализации. *Язык, сознание, коммуникация*// Москва: диалог-МГУ. 2000. 40-46.
3. Захаренко И.В., Красных В.В., Гудков Д.Б., Багаева Д.В. Прецедентное имя и прецедентное высказывание как символы прецедентных феноменов// см. наст. сборник.
4. Караулов, Ю.Н. *Русский язык и языковая личность*// Москва: ЛКИ, 1987.
5. Караулов Ю.Н. *Русский язык и языковая личность*// Москва: ЛКИ. 2010.

6. Шилаева Н.К. Методика обучения студентов пониманию прецедентных феноменов в иноязычных текстах как средства совершенствования социокультурной компетенции// Москва: автореферат. 2022.